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CURRENT TRENDS IN THE NEED TO STRENGTHEN THE SPIRITUAL AND IDEOLOGICAL PROPAGANDA AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE

Annotation: *This article discusses the features of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism and the work being done in this regard. At the same time, the relevance of the methods and tools used in the prevention of ideological influences to modern processes, as well as some recommendations in ideological education are put forward.*

Keywords: *propaganda, ideology, youth, education, unorganized youth, upbringing, spirituality, ideological education,*

Introduction

In recent years, the social activity of young people has been growing. In this regard, the social and ideological concepts and ideas that are formed in them are very important. It is important to form the ideology of national independence in the minds of young people, to educate the younger generation in the spirit of love for the Fatherland, the heritage of our ancestors, the idea of independence.

One of the main goals of our national ideology is to encourage our people and youth to work hard. Only through labor, through the development of the economy that will ensure the development of our society, and the creation of material wealth, will we be able to join the ranks of developed countries. Because if any idea is not based on practice and is not connected with labor, it loses its political power and, conversely, the idea, which is combined with labor, becomes the belief of the people.

At the heart of any sovereign state's policy is its own security. Uzbekistan's national security requires not only the protection of state sovereignty and territorial integrity by arms, but also to take active political and diplomatic measures to prevent war, to ensure the economic and technological security of the state, internal stability and peaceful coexistence, and to protect the legal, cultural and educational achievements of its citizens.

The negative impact of complex geopolitical and ideological processes is growing, and the struggle for the minds and hearts of the people is intensifying. Scientific research on these issues is carried out in a narrow range[1].

The stability, peaceful life, development and future of the state depend on the understanding of the nature of all threats that may pose a great threat to this country, the ability of our people to prevent and eliminate them. Calmness, drowsiness, or complete ignorance of a threat will inevitably lead to serious consequences.

Materials and methods

It is possible to observe how dangerous we are in contact with the world today. One of the reasons for the need to ensure the spiritual security of young people in our region is that the market economy, along with foreign investment, modern equipment and technology, methods of market formation, brings to our country its culture, lifestyle, worldview and imagination. It's a natural process, of course, and it can't be stopped by any obstacles. The youth of our country cannot be stopped from such influence by administrative means, even by legislation, and it affects our state, our people, the upbringing and worldview of the youth, and carries a great danger. It is important to note that those who seek to carry out their nefarious activities are trying to carry out propaganda work in any way possible.

The other side of the coin, unfortunately, is that we still have people who are spiritually poor, narrow-minded, and self-centered. These are the people who create the demand for opium. There are also young people who are blindly and sickly interested in the life of foreign countries. Actions in different directions, views formed under the influence of popular culture, are entering our country today and can have a negative impact on our youth. It is important to prevent them and not to poison the minds of our young people.

Here are some trends to keep in mind. In particular, the spiritual and ideological threat arises as a result of the social interaction of the object and the subject, and is carried out on the basis of a single social type collision of cultural and social bases. That is why today the issue of protection of spirituality and protection from contradictory, alien, destabilizing spirituality is very important.

The threat of global ideological threat and aggression lies in the fact that their access to our country is almost open. The rapid development of information technology and the great potential of satellite communications are exacerbating the problem.

There are several reasons for the need to ensure spiritual security in Uzbekistan. These include:

to return the newly formed young sovereign states to the old-fashioned "unitary state";

- aggression against the formation of national consciousness and national self-consciousness of peoples; It should be noted that there are various political, religious and extremist forces that are trying to destabilize the state, undermine the faith of our people and build a single Islamic state, using the existing natural difficulties. In order to prevent such threats, it is necessary, first of all, to ensure ideological security in Uzbekistan. Today, ideological landfills are even more powerful than nuclear landfills. In this situation, the people of Uzbekistan can argue against the idea against the idea, against the idea, against ignorance only with enlightenment. When we talk about threats, we must first turn our attention to the global problems that have intensified by the end of the twentieth century. Today, such problems include terrorism, drug abuse,

religious extremism, and fanaticism. According to official figures, there are more than 600 terrorist organizations in the world today. They have expanded their network to nearly 100 countries. Indeed, terrorism has become a serious threat in many countries and an international problem. In order to effectively combat this evil, it is necessary to develop new, unconventional forms and methods of struggle. In particular, IA Karimov noted that this serious threat is not sufficiently assessed, noting that a superficial approach to it is a serious political mistake. He said that the prevention of any aggression and terrorist attacks requires the elimination of their ideological ground and, above all, the struggle for the hearts and minds of our young people, for common sense [2].

The politicization of religion has always been and will continue to be a threat to human life. From the point of view of modern problems and pending solutions, these actions have never posed a greater threat to the well-being of all mankind than they do today. The essence and content of these movements and movements are expressed in the balance of adherents, support for inhumane ideas, and intolerance of other religious beliefs. In order to prove their veracity, such people resort to violence and murder, that is, they do not give up anything in order to achieve their goals. Terrorism, extremism, and bigotry have become global problems today.

There are now almost all sites of radical Islamic organizations on the Internet. Most sites have their own network on the Internet. It is, in a sense, a virtual jihad. Many of the sites promote jihadist ideas, anti-Western, and anti-Islamic regimes in Islamic countries. Islam is a value inherited from our ancestors. It is for us a set of laws of both faith and religion. Indeed, our state has restored our religious values and declared freedom of conscience.

On April 7, 1999, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the establishment of the Tashkent Islamic University" was issued. The main reason for the establishment of such a place is the growing curiosity and demand for the holy religion of Islam. The training and revitalization of professionals who properly propagate Islam will help prevent the population from being exposed to various religious extremist forces. This means that everyone who cares about the future of our country today should not be indifferent to the physical and mental poisoning of our peoples, especially our youth, with imported material and spiritual opium. What to do for this? So, we are committed to an alien, destabilizing ideology - the ideology of national independence, to physical suffering and bloodshed - kindness, to irreligion - spiritual purity, to obscenity - humility, to nonsense - spiritual wealth, in other words, to the centuries-old nature of our people. We must shield our Eastern morals, high spirituality and rich culture and values created during the development of our country. When we care about spiritual security, it is important to understand, first and foremost, the importance of building high morale in citizens. It is well-known that a nation with a high level of spirituality will prosper, move forward with confidence and courage, and,

conversely, a country or state that is spiritually poor will collapse. It will be necessary to be able to deeply analyze the socio-political, cultural and ideological processes taking place in the world, to master the mechanisms and technologies for the formation of national ideas and ideological immunity[3]. The important thing is to identify in the minds of young people the basic principles of preventing spiritual threats.

These principles include:

- The interconnectedness and integrity of the processes being studied
- Harmony of national and universal values;
- The priority of national interests in democratic development;
- Freedom of thought based on tradition and modernity (pluralism of opinion);
- Coordinating duties and responsibilities with practical activities.

It is a well-known principle that a leader is a person who manages the activities of the people on the basis of ethical norms, which are reflected in the life of the state and society. The principle of interdependence and integrity of social and political processes is an important aspect of leadership. It requires an assessment of the interests of the youth of our country, their current interests and interests, with the aspects that are at the heart of the process of globalization in the world today, especially in the Western world. In fact, the objects and phenomena of nature, society, and human thought are so dialectically interconnected that it is difficult to imagine them separately. This principle “represents the internal structural unity of all elements and events of all things and events in any holistic system, as well as the extremely diverse connections and relationships of that system with other systems or events surrounding it. It is well-known that society cannot live without ideology and purpose. First, ideology is necessary in the life of any society. Without ideology, a person, a society, a state will inevitably lose its way. Second, where there is an ideological vacuum, there will be an alien ideology. It is not difficult to cite many examples from history and modern times to prove this[4]. It is an important factor in leadership activities as a goal to society, a means to achieve it.

As President SH.Mirziyoyev said, "The ideology of the New Uzbekistan we are building will be an ideology of humanity, goodness and creativity"[5].

Consistent reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan, including the liberalization of the social system, the development of civil society institutions, require a new approach to youth in the country, which is moving towards a new society.

A market economy requires young people to be able to meet their own needs and solve most of life's problems on their own. Such social relations are forming a new consciousness in the personality of young people, and not taking it into account can also undermine the effectiveness of their upbringing. More precisely, the growing impact of the global information crisis and the need to protect against it, in this context, the immediate elimination of gaps in the minds of young people, strengthening public control over youth activities should be a priority for us.

In recent years, there has been an increase in the use of transparency in the arts, in the display of vulgar images on television, in movies, in the media, and in the promotion of nonsense and obscenity, and sometimes immorality. ” "Young people are such a social class that it is difficult to achieve a certain result, whether in the social or political spheres, without taking into account their specific characteristics. Young people have little experience in life, their worldview is unique, but they do not accept any mandatory values that do not correspond to their ideals. ” But confronting traditions that are not part of our long-standing mentality can eventually develop skills in the minds of young people[6].

In our opinion, the following series of measures should be taken to work with unorganized youth, to educate them in the spirit of patriotism and to form in them an active civic position:

First of all, to support the active policy of the state on youth employment. In particular, it is necessary to focus not only on the transfer of responsibility to public authorities, but also to increase the participation of the private sector and private entrepreneurs. At the same time, there is a need for a comprehensive program of open recruitment system for entrepreneurs. That is, it will be necessary to introduce incentives for entrepreneurs to use in the selection of personnel and to introduce their activities to the general public in the use of state-owned media, which today leads the media system;

Second, it is necessary to organize a series of programs to encourage non-organized youth in the field, to organize cultural and educational meetings, to organize cultural centers in each district and city, and, if necessary, in the neighborhoods, to meet their spiritual needs. This will ensure that young people who have graduated from art colleges and are not able to start their professional careers today are also able to work and be productive;

Third, with the support and direct initiative of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan, it is desirable to create active advocacy youth groups, attracting unorganized youth through active youth through the creation of all modern conditions for their activities.

Conclusions

In short, the following trends are observed in strengthening the spiritual propaganda among young people:

First of all, modern technologies of spiritual influence are widely used around the world. In particular, ICT and Internet resources are leading. Therefore, in the spiritual upbringing of young people, advanced technologies, which are strongly recognized by young people, should be widely used as a means of combating them;

Second, spiritual education should be youth-oriented. This is because there are many cases of marginalization and neglect among modern youth, especially those who are not covered by education;

Third, young people are trying to take advantage of opportunities created for their peers abroad. There is a growing interest in working and living abroad;

Fourth, outdated "patterns" of spiritual propaganda, traditional approaches, increase the indifference of young people. Therefore, it is necessary to support and widely promote the reforms initiated by the President to strengthen reading. In particular, in order to increase the level of reading among the population, first of all, the regions and cities annually hold competitions in such areas as "The most reading school", "The most reading neighborhood", "The most reading family". awarding valuable prizes, including domestically produced cars;

Fifth, it is necessary to reconsider the mechanisms to create the necessary conditions for the effective use of the creative abilities and potential of young people, especially non-organized youth. In particular, it is advisable to pay for creative works, and in this regard, to organize public procurement. The fact that some creative young people are influenced by "mass culture" or go abroad is related to these problem;

Sixth, the lives, thoughts, dreams and, most importantly, the issues that afflict young people, unfortunately, are not fully reflected in radio and television, newspapers and magazines.

In general, it is a complex system of measures to strengthen spiritual propaganda among young people. All factors must be taken into account in this system.

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